

THE ROLE OF COMPRESSION IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

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Annotation

In the fast-developing world, people tend to accomplish any task as fast as possible. This is how the simultaneous interpretation was brought to life. In the past when meetings, conferences were held among multilingual speakers, it was hard to deliver every point at the time of speaking. Therefore, consecutive translation needed to be developed to something more suitable for such occasions. Although simultaneous interpretation was invented in 1926, its official birthdate is considered to be 1945-1946, The Nuremberg trials. This allowed different language speakers understand each other without any disturbance, fairly smoothly.

Key words: compression, simultaneous interpretation, significance, the role.

Аннотация

В быстроразвивающемся мире люди стремятся выполнить любую задачу как можно быстрее. Так появился синхронный перевод. В прошлом, когда встречи, конференции проводились среди говорящих на нескольких языках, было трудно донести каждую мысль во время выступления. Поэтому последовательный перевод нужно было доработать до чего-то более подходящего для таких случаев. Хотя синхронный перевод был изобретен в 1926 году, официальной датой его рождения принято считать 1945-1946 годы, Нюрнбергский процесс. Это позволяло носителям разных языков понимать друг друга без каких-либо помех, достаточно плавно.

Ключевые слова: компрессия, синхронный перевод, значение, роль.

Looking at definitions of the word “translation”, we have almost the same description in all dictionaries. For instance, “[spoken](https://www.macmillandictionary.com/) or [written words](https://www.macmillandictionary.com/) that have been [changed](https://www.macmillandictionary.com/) into a [different language](https://www.macmillandictionary.com/)” [<https://www.macmillandictionary.com/>],¹ “a text or word that has been changed from one language into another” [<https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/>]², so on and so forth. Many consider translation as a word for word translation of a source language to the target one, however, we should not forget that sentence structures, styles, all vary from language to language, therefore, getting a translator do it, would cause a huge problem both for the translator and the target language reader. Let us, at this point, distinguish between the language from which a translation is being made and the language into which the translation is being made with the help of two technical terms. The language from which the translation is being made is called source language and the language into which the translation is being made is called target language or receptor language. If a translation adequately communicates the message of the original and is presented in a style similar to the original, it is expected that it will make an impression on its readers which is similar to the impression made by the original on its readers. This could be a possible objective, unless the translator has set up other goals as well. Generally speaking, a translator must translate into his/her mother tongue or the language of 'habitual use'. But this is not to say that s/he should not have sufficient competence in the language from which s/he is translating.

"Here, then, is the full process of **translation**. At one point we have a writer in a room, struggling to approximate the impossible vision that hovers over his head. He finishes it, with misgivings. Some time later we have a translator struggling to approximate the vision, not to mention the particulars of language and voice, of the text that lies before him. He does the best he can but is never satisfied. And then, finally, we have the reader. The reader is the least tortured of this trio, but the reader

¹ https://www.macmillandictionary.com

² <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com>

too may very well feel that he is missing something in the book, that through sheer ineptitude he is failing to be a proper vessel for the book’s overarching vision.”³(Michael Cunningham, "Found in Translation." *The New York Times*, Oct. 2, 2010).

Simultaneous interpretation uses the source text transformation method. The method of transformation of the source text in simultaneous translation aims to prepare the source text for operations at the formal sign level, that is, for the use of the sign method of translation, which R.K. Minyar-Beloruhev considers as the main method of simultaneous translation. They are the following:

- lexical transformations with the search for speech units included in the semantic (thematic) systems formed by the translator;
- grammatical transformations that take into account the most common and simple syntactic constructions of the target language;
- speech compression, which is achieved by using all possible types of transformation.⁴

Speech compression is “... such a compression of it, determined by the specific conditions of communication, in which only what is necessary for a given task of communication is retained in it, and everything else is swept aside”⁵.

In fact, speech compression is generated by the specific conditions of the simultaneous interpreter's activity (time constraints and the simultaneity of the processes of listening to the speaker's speech and generating speech in the target language), and its dimensions are determined by the need to maintain an even rate of

³ Michael Cunningham, "Found in Translation." *The New York Times*, Oct. 2, 2010

⁴ Миньяр-Белоручев Р. К. *Общая теория перевода и устный перевод*. М.: Воениздат, 1980

⁵ Арметов В.А. Психология обучения иностранным языкам. М 1-й МГПИИЯ 1966

the interpreter's speech in the target language. Speech compression, therefore, is a form of adaptation of translation actions to the conditions of activity ⁶.

In the theory and practice of translation, the principle of economy in language is most clearly manifested in compression. Compression in translation is carried out by converting the source text into a more concise form - by omitting redundant elements of the statement, i.e. elements replenished from the context and extralinguistic situation, as well as by using more compact forms of expression⁷.

Studies have shown that most often compression as a translation technique is used in simultaneous translation. Compression is usually used in cases where the rate of speech is high and the simultaneous interpreter cannot keep up with the speaker, because it is necessary not only to quickly interpret with a delay of no more than 1-3 seconds, but also at the same time process information received from the sender at the time of translation of the previous speech segment. Experimental data indicate that a message rate of 150-200 words per minute is the upper limit, after which any normal simultaneous translation is impossible.⁸

In particular, G.V. Chernov, identified the size of compression by comparing the compressed texts obtained as a result of simultaneous translation with uncompressed texts made in writing. As a result, it turned out that the compression during translation can reach 30-37%. The main factor influencing the size of the compression of the original message is the speed of the speaker's speech.⁹

Compression is typically used when:

- the pace of the speaker's speech is quite high;

⁶ Тункель В.Д. К вопросу об устной передаче речевого сообщения. Автореф. Диссертация 1965

⁷ Швейцер А.Д. Перевод и лингвистика: уч. для институтов и факультетов ин. яз. М.: Воениздат, 1973.

⁸ Горохова Л.А. Проблема оценки качества перевода Пятигорск, 2015. С. 124-132.

⁹ Chernov, «notebooks of interpreter” 1969

- there are repetitions in the original message;
- there are insignificant words in the original message;
- the speaker's thought can be expressed using fewer words.

Speaking about the methods of speech compression in simultaneous translation, it should be noted that it is carried out by means of synonymous or close to them replacements of words, phrases and sentences with shorter words, phrases and sentences, omission of segments that duplicate information contained in the previous context, omission of semantic units, redundant in a particular situation of communication, and the omission of semantic units that are redundant from the point of view of the task of communication, as well as generalization i.e. collapsing a syntagma to a word with a common meaning.¹⁰

The study of the features of simultaneous translation from the point of view of the preparation process and its direct implementation arouses research interest among domestic and foreign linguists, which is due both to the growing need for this type of interpretation in the context of the active development of economic, political and cultural ties between different states, and the increase quality requirements. Much attention on the part of researchers was paid to the study of psycholinguistic aspects of simultaneous translation (Kochkina Z.A., Chernov G.V.), psychological mechanisms of simultaneous translation, in particular, the mechanism of probabilistic forecasting (Ilyukhin V.M., Feigenberg I.M.), methods of teaching simultaneous translation (Visson L., Latyshev L.K., Semenov A.L.), which explain the special status of this type of translation. Over the past five years, studies have also been carried out that affect the psychological aspects of teaching simultaneous

¹⁰ Гурин И.В., Проблема речевой компрессии в синхронном переводе. Подходы и методы исследования. Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики. №1 (1) 2008. В 2 ч. Ч. 1 – Тамбов: «Грамота», 2008;

translation,¹¹ the theoretical foundations of simultaneous translation¹², in particular, the issues of using speech compression techniques in simultaneous translation¹³ and its phonetic aspects¹⁴, which shows the persistence of the relevance of the identified problems.

L. Wisson identifies the following cases when the translator has reasons to apply one or another method of speech compression:

1. There are repetitions in the original language.
2. There are words in the target language that don't mean anything.
3. The speaker speaks too fast.
4. The subject situation makes it possible to express the same thought in fewer words, which leads to time savings and, accordingly, the ability to more fully concentrate on incoming semantic groups¹⁵.

Conclusion

The active development of economic, political and cultural ties between different countries, as well as the scale of international cooperation in the field of education, science and art, make translation one of the most sought-after activities and at the same time increase the requirements for it. The era of globalization, information technology and the intensification of international contacts creates a growing demand for professional translators. As the need for simultaneous interpreters grows, it brings out question on how to improve interpretation skills. Thus, here comes compression in handy, since it is considered as one of the best methods to be used in simultaneous interpretation.

¹¹ Незнанов И.Н. Психологические аспекты обучения синхронному переводу // Вестник Южно-Уральского государственного университета. №12. 2015.

¹² Хромых А.А. Конференц-перевод (попытка осмысления теоретических основ) // Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики. – №9(74): в 2-х ч. Ч.1. 2017

¹³ Завьялова В.Л. Фонетические аспекты устного опосредованного перевода // Казанский педагогический журнал. – №6. 2015.

¹⁴ Афанасьева М.С. Употребление приемов речевой компрессии при синхронном переводе // Международный научный журнал «Символ науки» –№3. 2016.

¹⁵ Виссон. Л. Синхронный перевод с русского на английский. – М.: Р. Валент, 1999.

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12. Chernov, «notebooks of interpreter” 1969